

DETERMINING DRYING REGIMES FOR PREPARING PASTILA FROM APRICOT AND PLUM FRUITS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the importance of varieties, changes in the technological properties of fruits, different methods of drying, determination of the optimal modes of drying temperature and duration of drying, the effect of the drying process on the quality indicators of the finished product are studied in this article. Based on the results of the research, an effective technology of pastille deworming has been developed.

Introduction: Fruit pastille is an easily consumed and highly nutritious product obtained by drying fruit pulp or concentrated juice, with or without additives[1].

Basing the acceptable parameters of drying fruit and vegetable pastilles in an unconventional way, improving the principle scheme of the high-efficiency, energy-saving drying process and device for obtaining dried pastilles with different composition based on fruits and vegetables with a high moisture level, serves to determine technical and economic indicators, and reduce the loss of raw materials during processing[2].

The drying process is a key step in determining the physicochemical and organoleptic properties of pastilles. Although microwave drying is a fast method, high temperatures can lead to a decrease in biologically active substances. Vacuum drying, on the other hand, ensures better preservation of color and nutritional value. With increasing drying temperature and duration, a decrease in antioxidant activity and vitamin content is observed. It is also noted that the use of maltodextrin, pectin and other hydrocolloids improves texture and reduces stickiness. Aluminum foil and PET packaging have been shown to be more effective in maintaining the quality of pastilles for a long time [3].

Drying: The cooked mass is spread in a thin layer on a tray covered with parchment paper. Drying is carried out in two ways (natural and artificial). Dehydration of products in the open air is called natural drying, this process lasts a long time. In the food industry, artificial methods are also used to dry products, this process is carried out in special drying devices [4].

The primary preparation of high-quality dried fruits requires a clear strategic decision from the agricultural producer. As this necessitates planting varieties specifically cultivated

for drying, the approach must be correspondingly deliberate. For long-term storage, the moisture content of the dried fruit must be within the 12-18% range [4].

Discussion of the results. In pastille production technology, the drying process is considered one of the stages that most significantly impacts product quality. As a result of drying, the amount of free water in the product decreases, microbiological stability is ensured, shelf life is extended, and the texture of the product is formed. At the same time, the preservation of biologically active substances, natural color pigments, and aromatic compounds is of great importance during the drying process.

Therefore, when choosing drying technology, factors such as temperature, air velocity, relative humidity, the type of heat carrier, and product thickness are evaluated together.

In these studies, various drying technologies were applied to pastila samples prepared from the Subkhona and Isfarak apricot varieties, as well as the Vengerka and Stanley plum varieties. In the experiments, the pastila mass was applied to the surface of the PET substrate to a thickness of 3 mm, and convective (55°C), infrared, combined IR + convective, and natural solar energy-based drying technologies were applied (Table 1).

Table 1

Drying duration of apricot and plum pulp by variety

Variety	55°C convective	IQ	IR-Convective	Solar Dryer
Duration of drying, hours				
Subkhona	7,2	5,4	5,0	29,1
Isfarak	6,8	5,1	4,8	28,3
Vengerka	6,4	4,9	4,6	27,6
Stanley	6,1	4,7	4,4	26,9
Mix (60+40)	6,5	5,0	4,7	27,8

In pastille production technology, drying duration is considered one of the key technological indicators determining product quality, energy consumption, and production efficiency. Reducing drying time allows for increased production capacity, energy savings, and better preservation of the product's natural color and biologically active substances. From this perspective, the drying duration of pastillas from the Subkhona and Isfarak apricot varieties, as well as the Vengerka and Stanley plum varieties, was studied based on various technologies.

According to the data in Table 1, the drying duration significantly depended on the technology used and the characteristics of the raw material grade. Among all variants, the longest drying time was observed in the solar drying method, with indicators ranging from 26.9 to 29.1 hours. Specifically, the drying time for pastila prepared from the Subkhona variety was 29.1 hours, for the Isfarak variety 28.3 hours, for the Vengerka variety 27.6 hours, and for the Stanley variety 26.9 hours. The long duration of solar drying is explained by fluctuations in ambient temperature throughout the day, high relative air humidity, and incomplete control of the drying process. Additionally, the drying speed in this method depends on weather conditions.

In the convective drying method, moisture evaporation occurred more intensively under the influence of a 65°C temperature, and the drying time was reduced to 6.1–7.2 hours. The highest indicator was observed in the Subkhona variety (7.2 hours), and the lowest in the Stanley variety (6.1 hours). This is explained by the chemical composition of the varieties, the amount of dry matter, and the concentration of pectin substances. The relatively high content of pectin and dry matter in apricot varieties significantly slowed down moisture removal.

When using infrared (IR) drying technology, the drying time was further reduced, with indicators ranging from 4.7 to 5.4 hours. The drying intensity increased due to the fact that infrared radiation penetrated the inner layers of the product and accelerated the movement of moisture through the capillaries. As a result, an average of 20-25% time savings was achieved compared to convective drying.

In the experiment, the highest efficiency was recorded in the IR convective drying technology. In this technology, infrared radiation and a stream of hot air act simultaneously, accelerating the process of moisture removal from the product. Therefore, the drying time was 5.0 hours for the Subkhona variety, 4.8 hours for the Isfarak variety, 4.6 hours for the Vengerka variety, and 4.4 hours for the Stanley variety. These results are the lowest values among all variants (Fig. 1).

The degree of drying time reduction for the Stanley variety was calculated using the following formula:

$$\Delta t = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{t_1} \times 100$$

here:

- t_1 — solar drying time, hours;
- t_2 — IR convective drying time, hours.
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Calculation result:

$$\Delta t = \frac{26.9 - 4.4}{26.9} \times 100 = 83.6\%$$

Thus, when using IR-convective technology on the Stanley variety, the drying time was reduced by 83.6% compared to solar drying.

Figure 1. Drying methods and drying duration for apricot and plum fruits.

As can be seen from the presented results, the greatest reduction in drying duration was observed in the Stanley variety, while the lowest indicator was recorded in the Subkhona variety. However, in all variants, the reduction rate is around 82–84%, confirming the high efficiency of the technology.

Conclusion

Analysis of the varieties showed that the drying time of the Vengerka and Stanley plum varieties was shorter than that of the Subkhona and Isfarak apricot varieties. This may be due to the higher amount of free water in the plum fruit and the relatively low viscosity of the puree. Due to the high content of dry matter and pectin in apricot puree, moisture diffusion proceeded more slowly.

Overall, the research results showed that IR convective drying technology is the most optimal method for pastila production. This technology reduces drying time by an average of 83% compared to traditional solar drying, reducing energy consumption and increasing production efficiency. At the same time, the product possesses significant advantages in maintaining quality indicators.

References:

- 1.Santos, K. L., P. H. M. de Sousa, M. E. R. M. Cavalcanti- Mata, and L. B. de Vasconcelos. 2021. "Mixed Leather of açaí, Banana, Peanut, and Guarana Syrup: The Effect of Agar and Gellan Gum Use on Quality Attributes." *International Journal of Gastronomy and Food Science* 26: 100407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgfs.2021.100407>.
- 2.Kholikov M. M., Nasirova Sh. N. Effectiveness of improving the drying processes for fruit and vegetable pastilles // "The impact of digital technologies on the development of New Uzbekistan" international scientific and practical conference. - 2023. - Pp. 278-280.
- 3.Fruit Leather: Preparation, packaging and its effect on sensorial and physicochemical properties: A review. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 9(6), 1699-1709.

4. Aralova M.N. Technological parameters required for preparing dried plum pastels // "Current problems of hydraulic engineering construction and hydropower and their solutions" collection of the republican scientific-practical conference -2025. P- 674-677.
5. Ochilov M.A., Aralova M.N., and Menglimuratova I. Technological parameters required for the production of export-oriented dried products // special issue of international scientific journal science and innovation.-2024. P- 175-178.

